

ASSOCIATION OF AN AVM WITH AN ADJACENT IPSILATERAL MENINGIOMA: TWO CASE REPORTS

Mbaye Thioub MD-PhD¹, Fatou Sene MD¹, Daouda Wague MD-PhD¹, Ebrima K. Manneh MD²

¹Neurosurgery Department of Fann Teaching Hospital

(Centre Hospitalier National Universitaire Fann, Dakar, Senegal)

²Neurosurgery Departement of Edward Francis Small Teaching Hospital (Banjul, Gambia)

Correspondence: Dr Fatou Sene, Centre Hospitalier National Universitaire Fann

ABSTRACT

Objective: *This is a case of a rare association between an arterio-venous malformation and an adjacent meningioma. The aim was to do an exhaustive literature review, discuss the different therapeutic modalities and the pathophysiologic mechanisms that can explain such an association.*

Case Presentations: *A 44 years old patient, seen in our department for episodes of generalised tonic-clonic seizures, with a background of chronic headaches for the past two months. An angio-CT scan and an angio-MRI showed the presence of an AVM associated with an adjacent space occupying lesion. An indication for a concomitant resection by a left frontal craniotomy passing the midline was made. Histopathology came back in favour of a meningothelial and fibroblastic meningioma. The second case was a 37-year-old patient, seen for sudden onset of loss of consciousness preceded by a clinical picture of intracranial hypertension. The angio-CT scan showed an AVM Spetzler grade II and a calcified lesion of the falx cerebri suggestive of a meningioma was discovered intra-operatively.*

Conclusion: *The coexistence of an AVM and a meningioma is rare and is only rarely described in literature. Certain authors maintain that it is pure coincidence; while others hypothesize that there might be a causal relationship between AVM and meningioma. In our first case where the meningioma, adjacent to the AVM, was diagnosed few years after the latter, the hypothesis that the vascular malformation had induced the development of a meningioma is more likely.*

Keywords: Cerebral Vascular Malformation-Meningioma-Association-Literature-Case Report

Cite this Article: Mbaye Thioub, Fatou Sene, Daouda Wague, Ebrima K. Manneh, Association of An AVM with an Adjacent Ipsilateral Meningioma: Two Case Reports, International Journal of Neurosurgery (IJNEU), 2(1), 2024. pp. 1-8.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJNEU/VOLUME_2_ISSUE_1/IJNEU_02_01_001.pdf

INTRODUCTION

Cerebral vascular malformations constitute rare pathologies, considered congenital, and most often diagnosed in adults at an average age of 40 years. Their incidence is relatively low, varying between 1.12 – 4.12 % for 100.000 habitants par year[11, 15]. Its association with meningiomas, one of the most common primary central nervous system tumours in adults, is even more rare. Some school of thoughts maintain this association to be mere coincidence; while others maintain the existence of a causal link, especially if the two lesions are in close proximity (angiogenic and inflammatory phenomenon). To our knowledge, 20 cases of AVM associated with meningioma, including ours, had been described in literature[6]. We hereby report two cases of a frontal AVM associated with a meningioma and then discuss a few hypotheses intending to explain the pathophysiology behind such occurrence.

CASE PRESENTATIONS

FIRST CASE:

A 44 years old patient, followed up for an AVM since he was 13years of age and for hyperthyroidism for the past 6 years; who presented to our department with complains of gradual onset of intermittent headaches, progressively increasing in severity over the past two months, with no precipitating factors and associated with episodes of generalized tonic clonic convulsions, relieved by antiepileptic agents. Physical examination revealed a conscious patient, with monoparesis of the right lower limb of 4/5, with a pre-operative mRS score of 1. MRI with angiographic sequences (Figure 2) done two months prior to admission showed a posterior frontal left AVM attached to the falx cerebri, fed by the homolateral pericallosal artery and draining into the superior sagittal sinus classed as Spetzler grade III and Lawton 4. It was associated with a homolateral extra-axial lesion, attached to the dura mater at the level of posterior frontal convexity; hypo-intense on T1 and iso-intense on T2, with a mild increase in intensity after injection of Gadolinium suggestive of a meningioma, with the intra-cranial portion measuring 2.83 x 4.62 cm with significant hyperostosis. Following discussion and meticulous counselling a decision to concomitantly treat the two lesions was made.

Figure 1: Angio CT of brain, axial view(A) et sagittal view (B) coronal view(C) showing a left posterior frontal AVM draining into the sagittal sinus, in contact with a lesion (with uptake of contrast) with bone reaction of the left frontal convexity.

Figure 2: Angio-MRI of the brain, sequences T1(A), T2(B-C), T1 Gado (D-E) showing the left frontal AVM parafalcine, fed by the left pericallosal artery and attached to a lesion with uptake of contrast after injection with extra-cerebral extension

SURGICAL PROCEDURE

A craniotomy exposing both lesions was done. A flap going pass the midline was done and we were able to see the meningioma which was soft, which comes easily with suctioning, separated from the AVM by a thick layer of arachnoid matter which was beneficial as it helped protect against accidental opening of the AVM. Following a non-incident resection of the meningioma, the AVM was disconnected and resected. The procedure was complicated by rupture of the AVM leading to significant blood loss. The invaded bone was not put back, a cranioplasty with acrylic cement was done. The histopathology came in favour of a meningotheial and fibroblastic meningioma associated with an AVM.

Figure 3: intra-operative images showing the tumour (A, blue arrow), resting on a thick layer of arachnoid matter (B, yellow arrow) separating it from the AVM (C, black arrow).

EVOLUTION

Post operatively, there was worsening of the motor deficit with right hemiplegia, meningitis necessitating antibiotics, removal of the cranioplasty material and external ventricular drainage followed eventually by a ventriculo-peritoneal shunt. Patient declined second cranioplasty 6 months later. At the final follow up, the patient was able to walk without support with a mRS score of 3.

Figure 4: Post-operative brain CT scan showing the complete resection (A, B, C) with a clip in place. D: normal pressure hypertension. E: Post removal of the cranioplasty material following suppuration of the surgical site.

SECOND CASE

This was a 37 years old patient with a several months history of episodes of convulsions, not on treatment, who presented with sudden onset of loss of consciousness preceded by severe headaches associated with vomiting and followed by right sided weakness; two days prior to admission. On admission, he has a Glasgow of 15, a right sided hemiplegia with brachial predominance (UL 0/5 LL 1/5) and the mRS score estimate was 4. The brain CT scan with angiographic sequences showed a large left paramedian frontal hematoma, flooding the ventricles and leading to a subfalcine herniation on a left paramedian frontal AVM Spetzler grade II and Lawton 2 (Figure 5). A decision to cure the AVM was made and was to be done via a left frontal craniotomy going pass the midline.

Figure 5: Angio-Brain CT scan showing a compressive frontal hematoma(A) on a left paramedian AVM Spetzler grade II(B et C).

Upon resecting the AVM, we discovered a calcified lesion of approximately 2cm in diameter, attached to the falx cerebri, adjacent to the AVM, suggestive of a meningioma which we excised.

Post op CT scan was satisfactory. The post-operative period was unremarkable and the patient was discharged on day 8 post-surgery.

Figure 6: intra-operative images showing curing of the AVM (A, black arrow), excision of the draining vein (B, blue arrow) and excision of the calcified lesion (C, white arrow).

DISCUSSION

Intracranial meningiomas represent the most common primary tumours of the central nervous system representing 13 – 26 % of all tumours; contrary to AVM whose incidence is relatively low at about 1.12 – 1.42/100,000/year [15, 23]. For this reason, an association between these two entities; whose pathogenesis and natural history are different, is extremely rare: with incidence of 0.3% to 0.7% [23]. Certain authors like Cayli et al maintain the hypothesis that it is a pure coincidence in cases where there is some distance between the two lesions; while others hypothesize the existence of a causal relationship between the AVM and meningioma, suggesting that the hypervascularization of meningiomas is in part due to the neo-angiogenesis which would thereby lead to the formation of an AVM; that the prolonged irritation of the arachnoid cells surrounding the AVM could be the cause for the development of an adjacent meningioma and finally that there would exist a third environmental factor capable of simultaneously inducing these two lesions [3, 9, 13, 23].

Till date, the successive events leading to the formation of an AVM is not clearly defined: an inadequate communication during the embryonic period (between the 4th and 8th week of intrauterine life) at the moment when arteries and veins are juxtaposed (without capillary beds), and persisting after birth, would favour the genesis of an AVM. A subjacent genetic mutation has been equally strongly incriminated [10, 16]. These phenomena, associated with the secretion of angiogenic hormonal factors by endothelial cells, would favour the proliferation of this vascular anomaly. In fact, vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) known for its major role in vasculogenesis and angiogenesis is strongly expressed in AVMs [10]. Other factors such as Activin-receptor like kinase (ALK1), Transforming growth factor Beta (TGFB), Hypoxia-inducible factor (HIF), Platelet-derived growth factor, the Notch- signalling pathway recently (via a « wall shear stress »; inflammatory such as the Matrix- metalloproteinase 9 (MMP9), Angiopoietin 2 (AGP2), Interleukin 6 are equally implicated in the pathogenesis of AVMs but their mechanism of action remains to be elucidated [16, 22]. So until now, considered as a congenital and static lesion; the hypothesis of acquired AVMs (de novo) on a background of genetic predisposition, following a second event called « second hit » (trauma, tumours, inflammation, epilepsy, CVA, surgery ...) which set into motion a cascade of inflammatory responses and activate angiogenesis in an uncontrolled manner, is getting more and more raised by certain authors [10, 12, 14, 16, 21].

Cushing and Eisenhardt in their work suggested that chronic irritation of arachnoid cells due to lesions including AVMs could give rise to a meningioma[13, 20]. Likewise, some recent studies have proved the pathogenicity of factors such as VEGF, MMP9 in the evolution of meningiomas and the peritumoral oedema [4, 17].

Concerning the first case, the hypothesis according to which the AVM could induce an adjacent meningioma seems more plausible since the patient was followed up for the AVM since 13 years of age; and the meningioma was only diagnosed several years later. However, the hypothesis of the existence of a third factor having led to the development of the meningioma or that the occurrence is only merely coincidence cannot be excluded with certainty.

Due to the complexity of this association, the management should be well thought out, relying on well-defined criteria that depends mainly on the symptomatology of the patient and the risk of rupture of the AVM. It is demonstrated that the annual risk of rupture depending on the following characteristics of the AVM such as; deep location, association with a high flow aneurysm, deep drainage, and previous history of rupture, varies between 1,3-4,12% [6, 24]. For our first case; taking into account the risk of rupture which was not zero, the neurological deficit (spastic right lower limb monoparesis) added to a compressive meningioma, and its adjacent location to the AVM; a concomitant excision of the two lesions was done. Hong et al in their systematic review, had a total of 18 cases (Tableau 1) of AVMs associated with a meningioma from which 44%, were two adjacent or entangled lesions that benefitted from a concomitant excision [2, 6, 8, 9, 19]. On the other hand, associations of AVMs and meningiomas but of different locations (ipsilateral but distant, contralateral or above and below the tentorium cerebelli) reported in literature, benefitted from either excision in two different surgeries starting with the lesion that poses a higher risk to the patient's life or function, or isolated excision of the meningioma following correlating it to the symptomatology [3, 5, 6, 18].

Table 1: Cases of AVM including ours reported in literature, their location, relation and treatment modality

Cas	Authors	AVM location	Meningioma location	Relation	Treatment
1	Fukawa 1977[3, 6]	Parietal L	Parasagittal R	separate	AVM excision then meningioma
2	Kasantikul 1981[7]	Temporal R	Temporal R	entangled	concomitant
3	Kasantikul 1981[7]	Frontal R	Frontal R	entangled	concomitant
4	Kasantikul 1984[8]	Frontal R	Frontal R	entangled	concomitant
5	Ohno 1986[3, 6]	Parietal L	Frontal L	separate	Concomitant
6	Bitoh 1987[1]	Parieto-occipital R	Parieto-occipital R	entangled	concomitant
7	Soria 1990[20]	Temporo-parietal R	Occipital L	separate	nothing
8	Kadoya 1991[3, 6]	Parietal R	Ventricular R	adjacent	concomitant
9	Sawamura 1991[19]	Occipital R	Occipital R	Adjacent	concomitant
10	Shida 1995[6]	Para hippocampal R	Sphenoidal R	adjacent	concomitant
11	Castillo 1998[6]	Frontal L	Frontal L	NR	Meningioma excision
12	Çayli 2001[3]	Frontal L	Parietal L	separate	Meningioma excision
13	Moumen 2012[13]	Fronto-temporal R	Foramen Magnum	separate	Meningioma excision
14	Honeybul 2015[5]	Parietal L	Parafalcine frontal Post L	separate	Meningioma excision
15	Labidi 2015[9]	Parietal R	Parietal R	adjacent	concomitant
16	Boschi 2016[2]	Temporo-parietal R	Fronto-temporal R	adjacent	concomitant
17	Rubio 2020[18]	Tectal	Parafalcine posterior L	separate	Cure of AVM then meningioma excision
18	Hong 2020[6]	Temporal G	Petrous L	separate	Cure of AVM then meningioma excision
19	Our case 2024	Frontal R	Frontal R	adjacent	concomitant
20	Our case 2024	Frontal L	Parafalcine L	adjacent	concomitant

CONCLUSION

The coexistence of an AVM and meningioma is rare and is only scarcely reported in literature. The relationship that occasionally exists between these two lesions (adjacent, entangled) leaves the impression that exists a causal link, however the pathophysiologic mechanism needs further research. The management should be on a case-by-case basis taking into account the natural history of each lesion, the symptomatology sometimes similar (convulsions, headaches, neurological deficits), location (homolateral, contralateral, above or below the tentorium cerebelli) and the type of relationship (separate, adjacent, entangled, vascular connection).

The two cases presented here support the hypothesis of a causal connection between the two lesions and in our first case where the meningioma adjacent to the AVM was only diagnosed several years after the latter, the hypothesis according to which the vascular malformation had induced the development of a meningioma is more plausible.

REFERENCES

- [1] **Bitoh S, Hasegawa H, Kato A, Tamura K, Mabuchi E, Kobayashi Y.** *Meningeal neoplasms associated with cerebral vascular malformations.* Surg Neurol. 1987;27(5):469-475.
- [2] **Ashraf-Noubari B, Barbagli G, Boschi A, F. لوران س, et al.** *A Rare Association between Meningioma and Two Intracranial Vascular Lesions: Case Report and Review of Literature.* In: *Iranian Journal of Neurosurgery.* 2016. Disponible sur: <http://irjns.org/article-1-34-en.html>. p. 22-24.
- [3] **çayli SR, Sökmen Ü, Bulut T.** *Intracranial Arteriovenous Malformation Associated with Meningioma: An Unusual Case.* 2001;
- [4] **Hess K, Spille DC, Adeli A, Sporns PB, Zitta K, Hummitzsch L, et al.** *Occurrence of Fibrotic Tumor Vessels in Grade I Meningiomas Is Strongly Associated with Vessel Density, Expression of VEGF, PIGF, IGFBP-3 and Tumor Recurrence.* Cancers. 2020;12(10):3075.
- [5] **Honeybul S.** *Coexistence of an intracranial meningioma and an arteriovenous malformation.* J Surg Case Rep. 2015;2015(6): rjv061-rjv061.
- [6] **Hong MAC, Salonga AEM, Khu KJO.** *Coexistence of arteriovenous malformation and meningioma in a single patient: Systematic review and illustrative case.* J Clin Neurosci. 2021; 88:75-82.
- [7] **Kasantikul V, Brown WJ.** *Meningioangiomas in the absence of von Recklinghausen's disease.* Surg Neurol. 1981;15(1):71-75.
- [8] **Kasantikul V, Jan Brown W.** *Lipomatous meningioma associated with cerebral vascular malformation.* J Surg Oncol. 1984;26(1):35-39.
- [9] **Labidi M, Lapointe G.** *Intracranial Arteriovenous Malformation Embedded in a Meningioma – Case Report and Review of the Literature.* J Neurol Surg Part B Skull Base. 2014;75(S 01):A220.
- [10] **Lawton MT, Rutledge WC, Kim H, Stapf C, Whitehead KJ, Li DY, et al.** *Brain arteriovenous malformations.* Nat Rev Dis Primer. 2015;1(1):15008.
- [11] **Mohr JP, Parides MK, Stapf C, Moquete E, Moy CS, Overbey JR, et al.** *Medical management with or without interventional therapy for unruptured brain arteriovenous malformations (ARUBA): a multicentre, non- blinded, randomised trial.* The Lancet. 2014;383(9917):614-621.
- [12] **Morales-Valero SF, Bortolotti C, Sturiale C, Lanzino G.** *Are parenchymal AVMs congenital lesions?* Neurosurg Focus. 2014;37(3):E2.
- [13] **Moumen N, Arkha Y, El Hassani MR, Chakir N, El Khamlichi A, Jiddane M.** *Coexistence of intracranial meningiomas and vascular malformations: A fortuitous association or direct relationship?* Diagn Interv Imaging. 2012;93(1):67-71.

- [13] **Nagai Y, Anan M, Fujiki M.** Cerebral Arteriovenous Malformations as Acquired Lesions: Case Reports and Review of the Literature. *J Stroke Cerebrovasc Dis.* 2020;29(10):105157.
- [14] Ozpinar A, Mendez G, Abla AA. *Epidemiology, genetics, pathophysiology, and prognostic classifications of cerebral arteriovenous malformations.* 2017;143:5-13.
- [15] **Park H, Koh EJ, Lee EJ, Cheon J-E, Kim S-K.** An acquired cerebral arteriovenous malformation after brain abscess treatment: case report and a review of the literature. *Childs Nerv Syst.* 2021;37(9):2923-2926.
- [16] **Reszec J, Hermanowicz A, Rutkowski R, Turek G, Mariak Z, Chyczewski L.** Expression of MMP-9 and VEGF in Meningiomas and Their Correlation with Peritumoral Brain Edema. *BioMed Res Int.* 2015;2015:1-8.
- [17] **Rubio RR, Li X, Orselik A, Dubnicoff T, Raper D, Hervey-Jumper S, et al.** Supracerebellar Approach for Resection of a Falco tentorial Dural Arteriovenous Fistula with Pial Tectal Arteriovenous Malformation Component Associated with a Left Parafalcine Meningioma. *World Neurosurg.* 2020;137:337.
- [18] **Sawamura Y, Janzer RC, Fankhauser H, De Tribolet N.** Arteriovenous Malformation in Meningothelial Meningioma: Case Report. *Neurosurgery.* 1991;29(1):109-113.
- [19] **Soria E, Fine E, Hajdu I.** Association of intracranial meningioma with arteriovenous malformation. *Surg Neurol.* 1990;34(2):111-117.
- [20] **Tasiou A, Tzerefos C, Alleyne CH, Boccardi E, Karlsson B, Kitchen N, et al.** Arteriovenous Malformations: Congenital or Acquired Lesions? *World Neurosurg.* 2020;134:e799-e807.
- [21] **Tu J, Li Y, Hu Z.** Notch1 and 4 Signaling Responds to an Increasing Vascular Wall Shear Stress in a Rat Model of Arteriovenous Malformations. *BioMed Res Int.* 2014;2014:1-13.
- [22] **Wang X, Liu Y, Tang R-W, Tao Zhu Y.** Coexistence of Large Meningioma and Arteriovenous Malformation: A Case Report and Literature Review. *Curr Med Imaging Rev.* 2023;20:e100323214541.
- [23] **Wong J, Slomovic A, Ibrahim G, Radovanovic I, Tymianski M.** Microsurgery for ARUBA Trial (A Randomized Trial of Unruptured Brain Arteriovenous Malformation)–Eligible Unruptured Brain Arteriovenous Malformations. *Stroke.* 2017;48(1):136-144.

Citation: Mbaye Thioub, Fatou Sene, Daouda Wague, Ebrima K. Manneh, Association of An AVM with an Adjacent Ipsilateral Meningioma: Two Case Reports, *International Journal of Neurosurgery (IJNEU)*, 2(1), 2024. pp. 1-8

Abstract: https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJNEU_02_01_001

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJNEU/VOLUME_2_ISSUE_1/IJNEU_02_01_001.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com